

AHP-DENG'S Similarity based Optimization of Forming Parameters on Cupro-Nickel (90/10) Alloy during Single Point Incremental Process

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Abstract:- The optimization of the incremental sheet metal forming parameters for the Cupro-Nickel (90/10) alloy using the Analytical Hierarchy Process (AHP)-DENG'S Similarity Based method is presented in this paper. Experimental investigation on the formability of Cupro-Nickel sheet metal led to an increase in the forming limit during the Single-Point-Incremental-Forming-Process (SPIF). The major and minor strain values were measured after the Straight Groove Test (SGT) which was conducted along the three standard directions. The multiple-criteria decision-making is a well-organized optimization methodology which quantifies the intricate findings that give us the individual preferences for a different course of action. Deng's method for the multi-criteria approach in which the priorities were required to rank the best forming parameters of SPIF combined with the AHP. It aids in determining the decision-makers' final understanding of the issue and helps them find the best solution to achieve their objective. The operational parameters for forming are optimised, and the value that ranks highest is chosen for fracture analysis and reported.

Keywords: SPIF, Formability, SGT, AHP-Deng's Optimization, Fracture topologies.

I. INTRODUCTION

Cupro-Nickel (90/10) alloys were manufactured using solid-solution compositions including nickel in weights ranging from 2% to 30%. The C70600 alloy, which has a nickel content of 10%, is employed in heat exchangers and maritime valves made from moulds. Improved corrosion resistance is a result of the addition of low quantities of chromium and manganese, and this characteristic is crucial for power plants and desalination plants alongside the coast. The restoration and eco-friendly capability of Copper alloys is an economic advantage by combining lighter load with greater thermal conductivity.[1]

The thermal - mechanical treatments on rapidly solidified and corrosion-resistant cupro-nickel alloys resulted in highly refined structure and uniform refined precipitation which exhibit excellent combinations of strength and ductility. The excellent and unusual softening resistance at high temperature occurred and the alloy undergo hardening during quenching from the room temperature. The tensile study demonstrates the Cu-Ni alloy's responsiveness to cold work and microstructure, which led to tiny grain size and substantially less segregation. Extensive research was required to fully

understand the phase transformation caused by the alloying components [2].

In the study conducted by [3], the mechanical properties and formability analysis of the copper-nickel (90/10) alloy were studied by chemical composition analysis, microstructure, tensile test, and Straight Groove Test along three directions. When compared to conventional forming processes, Single-Point Incremental Forming (SPIF) gives an improved forming limit, and the forming limit diagram plotted with the major and minor strain values supports the enhancement in forming limit. The highly precipitated grain size is a result of the microstructure and the components present, according to the chemical composition study. The tensile tests show the increase in ultimate tensile strength as compared to pure copper and improved formability can be obtained by conducting.

In order to choose the two best options, [4] estimated the degree of similarity among the alternatives for the multi-criteria inquiry. The degree of similarity between the positive and negative ideal solutions is highest and lowest, respectively, when the preferred option is selected. The similarities between the best solution and alternate magnitude and gradient were used to assess the overall performance indices for all criterions. This approach provides a ranking for multicriteria substitutes when it comes to tackling various multi-criteria problems.

By using SPIF and the Box-Behnken design for Multi-Objective Optimization, [5] investigated the effects of various process parameters on EDD steel sheets. The response variables for the quadratic model developed are mutually exclusive in nature and the most suitable to analyse manufacturing time and surface roughness during ISF. The study's conclusion suggests that the Pareto front can be used to pick the right set of process parameters efficiently.

In order to combine the priorities in a hierarchical structure and adhere to clear arguments in scaling challenges, the philosophy of making intelligent judgments must be followed. The analytical hierarchy technique for making judgments frequently employs the multicriteria decision making approach for organizing the components. The basic scale assigns the factors chosen for pairwise comparison a level of intensity of importance.[6]Relative scales are used in AHP to represent the subjective understanding where relative scales derive data from a standard scale to perform arithmetic operations. The two types of measurement, relative and absolute measurements are used in paired comparisons and descriptive and normative standard settings are also used.

The Taguchi AHP-DENG approach uses the technology of multi-criteria decision making to obtain quality criteria for the ideal process parameters. The process parameters of the SKD11 Die-Steel with titanium powder PMEDM (Powder Mixed Electrical Discharge Machining) were multi-objective optimized. PMEDM chose the White Layer Thickness(WLT), Surface Roughness(SR), Tool Wear Rate(TWR), and Material removal rate (MRR) as the quality standards for the machined surface. Results from DENG were compared to PSI, TOPSIS, and GRA. The authors came to the conclusion that the DENG'S result was preferable to the previous three optimisation methods [7].

The formability analysis of AA5052 using the Single-Point-Incremental-Forming-Process (SPIF) to investigate the influence of the forming factors[8]. The Straight Groove Test was carried out along the three directions of rolling, diagonal, and transverse using the L18 orthogonal array to formulate the forming parameters. The sum of stresses and the measured surface roughness were used as Multi-Objective response variables during the optimization of the SPIF parameters using Taguchi-GRA in conjunction with PCA. The outcomes supported an increase in formability along the rolling direction and an increase in surface roughness along the diagonal directions.

Honar [9] carried out the Single-Point-Incremental-Forming-Process experiments and the numerical analysis of bonded sheet metal. A formability analysis was done on the bi-metal bonded sheet created by explosively welding together pure copper sheet and AA1050 sheet. A multi-response optimization method is used to analyze the fracture depth and wall thickness and optimise the responses. Maximum fracture depth and wall thickness are achieved during the incremental forming process on the copper side. Higher percentages of confidence intervals were produced by the prediction models employing the RSM technique.

A new modified approach known as the DENG'S-Similarity method, which is a modified version of the Deng's method, was developed by [10] and used Multiple-Attribute-Decision-Making (MADM) to help make decisions from a number of decision criteria. Effective application of the theory of the perfect solution shows that the most favoured option has the highest and lowest degree of similarity, with the total performance index being derived from the similarity results. The results were superior to those from the TOPSIS method, and the suggested multi-criterion method can adequately describe genuine multicriteria analysis issues.

According to the author[11] investigation on the future of industry, incremental forming offers a greater chance for automation, but the process is difficult to complete because it moves slowly and has poor accuracy. In the formability analysis, pure copper sheets that are readily accessible on the market are used together with various process forming factors. The use of multiple sheets created using single point incremental forming allows for a faster manufacturing rate. In order to create the optimal solution for the input constraints, the hybrid optimization technique is used in conjunction with Taguchi-Grey-Relational Analysis (T-G-R-

A) and Response-Surface-Methodology (R-S-M). Based on the outcomes, an increase in the GRG value demonstrates that the hybrid optimization method can be used to the metal forming process.

The Single-Point-Incremental-Forming-Process (SPIF), which is necessary to meet the continuously rising demand in manufacturing industries and the development of novel sheet metal-based components, is a suitable substitute for the stamping process. The Wall Angle Test and the Straight Groove Test are the two methods for evaluating formability. The maximum wall angle that a material may be shaped into without fracture serves as a gauge for its formability. The highest recorded S/N ratio for the greater wall angle value indicates the response's highest quality attributes. The two factors with the greatest influence and least contribution are the tool diameter and feed rate [12].

Due to its superior mechanical qualities, aluminum-based metal matrix composites are used in the aerospace and defence industries. Abrasive reinforcements and tool wear are inescapable problems that result in subpar goods and prolonged manufacturing times. By using the AHP-DENG'S similarity based approach developed by [13], the drawback can be solved with the right kind of machining process. In order to obtain the best results from WEDM trials, the AHP-DENG optimization method is employed while taking the process parameters into account. The feasible solution for the WEDM responses were obtained.

Sen [14] investigations of the heat-resistant superalloy Inconel 690's implausible stiffness and poor machinability features led to these conclusions. In accordance with earlier literature evaluations, the machining was done using the least amount of vegetable oil lubrication possible. To determine the most efficient end milling parameters, Pareto-Hybrid Multi-Objective Optimization was utilised. The Non-Dominated Sorting-Genetic-Algorithm-II (NSGA-II), Technique for Order-Preference by Similarity to Ideal Solution Model (TOPSIS), and Gene Expression Programming (GEP) three computational techniques were combined. An ANOVA table is used to present the statistical analysis of the end milling components, and an estimated contribution % to the final outcome is given. The GEP-coupled NTOPSIS model gives the very low values of machining responses with greater accuracy.

A study was conducted using the hybrid Taguchi-AHP-DENG'S Similarity-Based Method on the multi-objective optimization of process constraints for the SKD11, Die-Steel using Electrical-Discharge-Machining (E-D-M) method. The electrode material used in the E-D-M method was copper, while the dielectric fluid used was D323 oil. For the purpose of calculating the results, the workpiece's mass, surface hardness, and roughness values were computed and their average values taken into account. The empirical findings indicated that the hybrid model could be used to address problems involving several objectives, and the findings also indicated that EDM with various materials and the micro-edm process were appropriate [15].

The following points were comprehended based on the literature review. Die-Steel, Aluminum and its composites,

and Copper and its alloys have received the most research on the AHP-DENG'S method [5–15]. There are no studies for optimization on Cu-Ni alloy, and only a small number of researchers have used the multi-criteria optimization strategy for the Copper alloy. AHP-Similarity DENG's Optimization was carried out for these reasons. The main objective of the current research is to optimize the Cu-Ni (90/10) alloy Straight Groove Test process parameters by SPIF. Tensile strength and ductility have improved in the Cupro-Nickel alloy's mechanical characteristics. The AHP-Deng strategy was selected in order to obtain optimum value

since it allows for the optimization of numerous criteria.

II. MATERIALS AND METHODS

In this study, formability in the single-point incremental moulding process was experimentally explored for the Cupro-Nickel (Cu-Ni 90/10) alloy of 1 mm thickness that was purchased in annealed state (SPIF). Using optical emission spectroscopy (OES) and the test references from BS EN 1507:2015, the chemical composition was determined. The results are shown in Table 1.

Material	Thickness (mm)	Percentage of Elements (in weight %)								
		Cu	Ni	Fe	Mn	Co	P	Pb	Zn	Sn
Cupro-Nickel	1	86.846	10.215	1.778	0.848	0.036	0.015	0.012	0.010	0.001

Table 1: Chemical composition of Cu-Ni 90/10 (C70600) (in weight %)

III. STRAIGHT GROOVE TEST (SGT)

The formability analysis of the Cu-Ni alloy was performed by the Straight Groove Test, using two different-ended tools to make the groove of 40 mm length in a sheet of 1 mm thickness along with the standard three directions i.e. Rolling-(0°), Diagonal-(45°) and Transverse-(90°) respectively. The fixture with a sheet clamped assembly and

the tool fixed in the spindle of the CNC milling machine assembly is shown in the Figure 1. Two different tools were used; one is a hemispherical ended tool (H-tool) and another one is a ball attached tool (B-tool) and Table 2 gives the forming parameters. After the completion of 18 experiments, the strain values are measured along with the lengthwise and breadthwise directions.

S.No	Factor	Parameter	Level 1	Level 2	Level 3
1	A	Tool	H	B	-
2	B	Ball dia(mm)	8	10	12
3	C	Speed (RPM)	300	450	600
4	D	Feed (mm/min)	300	600	900
5	E	Lubricants	Oil	Grease	Dry

Table 2: Influential parameters for Straight Groove Test

Fig. 1(a): CNC milling machine with fixture

Fig. 1(b): Incremental fixture with sheet metal

Fig. 1(c): Hemispherical and Ball attached tool

Fig 1(d): Straight grooves formed by tools

Fig. 1: (a-d): Incremental forming experiment details

To achieve the most reliable SPIF parameters the multi-criteria optimization technique is used. The control factors for this study are Tool Type[A], Tool Diameter[B],

Speed[C], Feed[D], and Lubricants[E] in which tool type is considered as two levels only and all other factors are three levels each.

Ex. No.	Taguchi - L18 - Mixed Level For 5 Factor										
	A	B	C	D	E	Exp. Label No	Tool type [A]	Ball diameter [B] (mm)	Speed [C] (RPM)	Feed [D] (mm/min)	Lubricants [E]
1	1	1	1	1	1	1H	H	8	300	300	Oil
2	1	1	2	2	2	2H	H	8	450	600	Grease
3	1	1	3	3	3	3H	H	8	600	900	Dry
4	1	2	1	1	2	4H	H	10	300	300	Grease
5	1	2	2	2	3	5H	H	10	450	600	Dry
6	1	2	3	3	1	6H	H	10	600	900	Oil
7	1	3	1	2	1	7H	H	12	300	600	Oil
8	1	3	2	3	2	8H	H	12	450	900	Grease
9	1	3	3	1	3	9H	H	12	600	300	Dry
10	2	1	1	3	3	10B	B	8	300	900	Dry
11	2	1	2	1	1	11B	B	8	450	300	Oil
12	2	1	3	2	2	12B	B	8	600	600	Grease
13	2	2	1	2	3	13B	B	10	300	600	Dry
14	2	2	2	3	1	14B	B	10	450	900	Oil
15	2	2	3	1	2	15B	B	10	600	300	Grease
16	2	3	1	3	2	16B	B	12	300	900	Grease
17	2	3	2	1	3	17B	B	12	450	300	Dry
18	2	3	3	2	1	18B	B	12	600	600	Oil

Table 3: Forming parameters using L18 Orthogonal array

The responses calculated from the SGT results were Major strain (Ma. St), Minor strain (Mi. St), Forming time (FT) and Depth of forming (DoF) for optimization. The broad priorities were calculated from the possible values and

their contributions in achieving the goal. Table 3 shows the levels and the diagram give the fracture of sheet formed after the straight groove tests and a sample strain measurement is given in the Figure 2.

Fig 2(a) Strain measurement using elongated circles

Fig 2(b) Major and Minor diameters

Fig. 2 (a-b): Sample strain measurements after the fracture

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In this work, the AHP-DENG similarity approach is used, which gives us the ability to express and quantify complex findings in alternative solutions and also give us a clear knowledge of individual preferences. The results were

summarised in Table 4 along with the SGT responses. Using this effective methodology, the best formed groove was determined, and the top-ranked experimental groove was chosen for fracture investigation.

Exp.no	Taguchi - L18 - mixed level for 5 factor											
	Rolling Direction				Transverse Direction				Diagonal direction			
	$\epsilon_{cor D1}$ [Ma. St]	$\epsilon_{cor D2}$ [Mi. St]	Time in min [FT]	Depth in mm [DoF]	$\epsilon_{cor D1}$ [Ma. St]	$\epsilon_{cor D2}$ [Mi. St]	Time in min [FT]	Depth in mm [DoF]	$\epsilon_{cor D1}$ [Ma. St]	$\epsilon_{cor D2}$ [Mi. St]	Time in min [FT]	Depth in mm [DoF]
1H	0.6150	0.0640	6.42	12.15	0.431	0.069	6.37	12.10	0.7190	0.0720	6.50	12.20
2H	0.5240	0.0810	5.11	12.7	0.473	0.077	7.01	12.4	0.6120	0.0610	5.35	15.70
3H	0.6800	0.0510	3.03	10.9	0.621	0.059	5.32	10	0.4970	0.0460	2.51	13.60
4H	0.8130	0.0760	8.45	15.7	0.475	0.089	6.14	13.3	0.5480	0.0650	9.42	17.80
5H	0.6450	0.0650	4.38	13.6	0.328	0.082	5.49	11.2	0.5890	0.0740	4.47	14.80
6H	0.6170	0.0710	2.48	12.2	0.519	0.075	4.31	9.1	0.4580	0.0760	4.01	10.50
7H	0.8850	0.0920	4.49	15.1	0.759	0.081	7.09	13.9	0.4250	0.0860	5.45	11.40
8H	0.7440	0.0890	3.2	13.3	0.683	0.076	2.45	13	0.6890	0.0890	7.30	17.20
9H	0.5640	0.0910	6.2	10.3	0.553	0.073	6.3	10.6	0.6470	0.0790	9.01	14.20
10B	0.7290	0.0670	3	13.3	0.566	0.059	2.57	13.3	0.7110	0.0920	6.27	15.70
11B	0.7100	0.0490	7.54	13.3	0.753	0.061	7.1	12.1	0.6340	0.0630	9.49	15.70
12B	0.5880	0.0510	4.23	13.9	0.732	0.067	3.58	13.9	0.6290	0.0780	6.02	16.80
13B	0.5740	0.0070	4.18	13.9	0.652	0.071	4.18	13.9	0.7630	0.0770	5.31	17.20
14B	0.7560	0.0670	3.1	15.1	0.721	0.060	3.2	14.8	0.5070	0.0590	3.45	16.60
15B	0.7870	0.0480	9.01	15.1	0.705	0.072	6.84	13.5	0.6520	0.0830	7.82	17.80
16B	0.2850	0.0660	3.31	16.6	0.727	0.066	3.27	16.3	0.7380	0.0560	9.41	15.20
17B	0.8280	0.0470	7.2	14.3	0.719	0.066	8.5	15.8	0.7440	0.0510	10.36	16.25
18B	0.9800	0.0410	5.26	18.1	0.523	0.571	4.4	6.9	0.7120	0.0420	6.46	16.89

Table 4: Straight Groove Test results of all three directions

A. Optimization of Forming Parameters

The Analytic-Hierarchy-Process (A-H-P) is an organised method for defining and assessing complicated decision problems. It offers a comprehensive and well-balanced framework for structuring a choice problem, figuring out its component pieces, connecting the foundations to overarching objectives, and assessing an alternate solution. It is possible to relate the hierarchical components to any aspect of the choice problem, and they are frequently estimated in the value that is least connected to the current conclusion. AHP-similarity Deng's algorithm was used to optimise the Straight Groove Test responses. According to

the above-mentioned experiment, this optimization approach produces the best-formed groove.

B. Design of Weightages for Straight Groove Parameters

The weights are framed by the pairwise comparison matrix, and the relative weights of each parameter are determined by Saaty's scale. To build the pairwise comparison matrix for the SGT replies, the four criteria are applied. Table 8 lists the four criteria in the following order: Major Strain, Minor Strain, Forming Time, and Depth of Fracture. The entire procedure is divided into the successive phases for calculating the weights, which also involve converting the priority vector to pairwise comparisons and then to a pairwise comparison matrix.

- **Stage I:** Framing the pair wise comparison matrix for each responses.

S.no	Rating	Preferred Judgement with explanation
1	1	Equally Preferred
2	3	Moderately Preferred
3	5	Strongly Preferred
4	7	Very Strongly Preferred
5	9	Extremely preferred
6	2,4,6,8	Intermediate Preferred Judgement
7	1/2,1/3, 1/4,1/5,1/6,1/7,1/8,1/9	Reciprocal of the preferential judgement. For example not moderately preferred is rated as 1/3, like this so on.

Table 5: AHP Scale for pair wise comparison

Criteria	Major Strain [Ma.St]	Minor strain [Mi.St]	Forming time in mins [FT]	Depth of forming in mm [DoF]
[Ma.St]	1	1/3	1/7	1/9
[Mi.St]	3	1	1/5	1/7
[FT]	7	5	1	1/3
[DoF]	9	7	3	1

Table 6: Pairwise comparison matrix table for SGT responses

- **Stage II:** The Eigen vectors(EV), found out by geometric mean method to get better priorities. Eigen vectors for the SGT responses were tabulated in Table 7. The following are the Eigen vectors of SGT responses i.e, Ma St, Mi. St, FT and DoF.

$$EV_{Ma.St} = \sqrt[4]{1 * \frac{1}{3} * \frac{1}{7} * \frac{1}{9}} = 0.2697; \text{-(a)}$$

$$EV_{Mi.St} = \sqrt[4]{3 * 1 * \frac{1}{5} * \frac{1}{7}} = 0.5411; \text{-(b)}$$

$$EV_{FT} = \sqrt[4]{7 * 5 * 1 * \frac{1}{3}} = 1.8481; \text{-(c)}$$

$$EV_{DoF} = \sqrt[4]{9 * 7 * 3 * 1} = 3.7078; \text{-(d)}$$

Stage III: The Priority weights (PW) are calculated by taking the ratio of Eigen vector normalization values by the summation of all column elements. The calculated Priority weights for SGT responses are tabulated below.

$$PW_{Ma.St} = 0.2697/6.3667 = 0.0424; \text{-(a)}$$

$$PW_{Mi.St} = 0.5411/6.3667 = 0.0850; \text{-(b)}$$

$$PW_{FT} = 1.8481/6.3667 = 0.2902 ; \text{-(c)}$$

$$PW_{DoF} = 3.7078/6.3667 = 0.5823; \text{-(d)}$$

Stage IV: Determination of Principal-Eigen-Value(PEV)

The summation of each column values when multiplied with their equivalent priority weights of each rows and summing up the results provides the Principal-Eigen-Value (λ_{max}) and illustrated in the following equation (i)

$$\lambda_{max} = \sum_{i=1}^n T_i * PVi \tag{i}$$

Criteria	Major Strain [Ma.St]	Minor strain [Mi.St]	Forming time in mins [FT]	Depth of forming in mm [DoF]	Eigen Value [EV]	Priority Weightages [PW]
[Ma.St]	1	1/3	1/7	1/9	0.2697	0.0424
[Mi.St]	3	1	1/5	1/7	0.5411	0.0850
[FT]	7	5	1	1/3	1.8481	0.2902
[DoF]	9	7	3	1	3.7078	0.5823
Total T_i	20	13.33	4.32	1.59	6.3667	
λ_{max}	$\sum_{i=1}^n T_i * PVi = 4.1607$					

Table 7: Pairwise comparison matrix table for SGT responses

$$\lambda_{max} = (20*0.0424+13.33*0.0850+4.32*0.2902+1.59*0.5823) = 4.1607$$

- **Stage V:** Estimation of Relative Consistency or Consistency index (CI)

The following equation (ii) is used to find the Consistency Index (CI). In this calculation as we have selected four criteria the selected value for n is 4.

$$C.I = (\lambda_{max}-n) / (n-1) \tag{ii}$$

$$C.I = (4.1607-4) / (4-1) = 0.0536$$

• **Stage VI:** Design of Consistency-Ratio (CR)
 The Consistency-Ratio (CR) was found out by the ratio of Consistency Ratio (CI) to Random-Consistency-Number. The Random Index table for different n values is tabulated below in Table 9. For n=4 the estimated Random Index

value is 0.8816. The value of CR should be below 0.1 is acceptable;

$$CR (A) = (CI (A)/RI_n) = (0.0536/0.8816) = 0.0608$$

N	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
RI	0	0	0.5247	0.8816	1.1086	1.2479	1.3417	1.4057	1.4499	1.4854

Table 8: Random Index Table for different matrix order (n)

When the Consistency Ratio is below 10%; therefore the Pair-Wise Comparison Matrix is satisfactory. The required weights determined for the output responses as follows.

$$W_{Ma.St} = 0.0424; W_{Mi.St} = 0.0850; W_{FT} = 0.2902; W_{DoF} = 0.5823.$$

C. *DENG'S Optimization of straight groove test parameters*
 Deng introduced the similarity based approach method and followed the steps below

• **Stage I:** Design of decision matrix
 The decision matrix with alternatives A_i ($i=1, 2, \dots, n$) against set of criteria C_j ($j=1, 2, \dots, m$) was designed and presented in the Table 7

• **Stage II:** Determination of weightages for SGT responses. The weightages were found out by AHP method for each single response.

$W_{Ma.St} = 0.0424$	$W_{Mi.St} = 0.0850$	$W_{FT} = 0.2902$	$W_{DoF} = 0.5823$
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• **Stage III:** Estimating the Normalized Decision Matrix values using the given equation (iii) table

$$r_{ij} = \left[\frac{x_{ij}}{\sqrt{\sum_{j=1}^m x_{ij}^2}} \right] \tag{iii}$$

$$V_{ij} = W_{ij} * r_{ij} \tag{iv}$$

• **Stage IV:** Determination of Performance Matrix
 The Performance Matrix was found by multiplying the Normalized Decision Matrix with the weightages calculated as illustrated by the equation iv.

• **Stage V:** Estimation of Positive (or Negative) Ideal Solution (PIS) and (NIS).
 The Positive (or Negative) Ideal Solution (PIS) and (NIS) are found out using eq. (v) (vi)
 Positive Ideal Solution (PIS): $A^+ = (Y_1^+, Y_2^+, \dots, Y_m^+)$ where $Y_j^+ = \max_{i=1,2,3,\dots,n} Y_{ij}$ (v)
 Negative Ideal Solution (NIS): $A^- = (Y_1^-, Y_2^-, \dots, Y_m^-)$ where $Y_j^- = \min_{i=1,2,3,\dots,n} Y_{ij}$ (vi).

RollingPIS	A^+	0.01528	0.0034	0.0299	0.0995
RollingNIS	A^-	0.00717	0.0442	0.1019	0.1748
TransversePIS	A^+	0.01267	0.0055	0.0279	0.0734
TransverseNIS	A^-	0.00542	0.0769	0.0804	0.1734
DiagonalPIS	A^+	0.01214	0.0113	0.0227	0.0898
DiagonalNIS	A^-	0.00757	0.0227	0.0937	0.1522

Table 9: PIS and NIS values for rolling, transverse and diagonal directions

• **Stage VI:** Finding of the conflict index between the alternates and the PIS and NIS

$$\cos\theta_{i+} = \frac{\sum_{j=1}^m Y'_{ij} Y_j^+}{\left(\sum_{j=1}^m Y_{ij}^2 \sum_{j=1}^m Y_j^{+2} \right)^{1/2}} \tag{vii}$$

$$S_i^+ = \frac{\left(\sum_{k=1}^m Y_{ik}^2 \right)^{1/2} \cos\theta_{i+}}{\left(\sum_{j=1}^m Y_j^{+2} \right)^{1/2}} \tag{ix}$$

$$\cos\theta_{i-} = \frac{\sum_{j=1}^m Y'_{ij} Y_j^-}{\left(\sum_{j=1}^m Y_{ij}^2 \sum_{j=1}^m Y_j^{-2} \right)^{1/2}} \tag{viii}$$

$$S_i^- = \frac{\left(\sum_{k=1}^m Y_{ik}^2 \right)^{1/2} \cos\theta_{i-}}{\left(\sum_{j=1}^m Y_j^{-2} \right)^{1/2}} \tag{x}$$

The θ value lies between 0° to 90° .

• **Stage VII:** Finding the Degree of Similarity between each alternates with the PIS and NIS.

- **Stage VIII:** Computing the Overall Performance Index for each alternative across all criteria

$$P_i = \frac{s_i^+}{s_i^+ + s_i^-}, i=1, 2 \dots n \dots \dots \dots (xi)$$

- **Stage IX:** Descending order ranking of the alternatives based on the index value.

The Performance Matrix Calculation, Positive and Negative Ideal Solution with their Conflict Index, Degree of alternates' similarity with PIS and NIS, overall performance index and their ranking for all three directions was presented in Table 12 to 14 respectively.

Exp. No	Taguchi - L18 - Mixed level for 5 Factors											
	Rolling direction				Transverse direction				Diagonal direction			
	Normalized values				Normalized values				Normalized values			
	Ma.St	Mi.St	FT	DoF	Ma.St	Mi.St	FT	DoF	Ma.St	Mi.St	FT	DoF
1	0.200	0.055	0.267	0.202	0.157	0.076	0.249	0.221	0.256	0.156	0.203	0.179
2	0.170	0.070	0.212	0.211	0.172	0.085	0.274	0.226	0.218	0.132	0.167	0.230
3	0.221	0.044	0.126	0.181	0.226	0.065	0.208	0.183	0.177	0.100	0.078	0.200
4	0.264	0.065	0.298	0.260	0.173	0.098	0.240	0.243	0.195	0.141	0.293	0.261
5	0.210	0.056	0.182	0.226	0.119	0.090	0.214	0.205	0.210	0.161	0.139	0.217
6	0.201	0.078	0.103	0.202	0.189	0.083	0.168	0.166	0.163	0.165	0.125	0.154
7	0.288	0.079	0.186	0.250	0.277	0.089	0.277	0.254	0.151	0.187	0.170	0.167
8	0.242	0.076	0.133	0.221	0.249	0.084	0.096	0.237	0.245	0.193	0.227	0.252
9	0.183	0.078	0.257	0.171	0.201	0.081	0.246	0.194	0.230	0.172	0.281	0.208
10	0.237	0.058	0.125	0.221	0.206	0.065	0.100	0.243	0.253	0.200	0.195	0.230
11	0.231	0.042	0.313	0.221	0.274	0.067	0.277	0.221	0.226	0.137	0.296	0.230
12	0.191	0.044	0.176	0.231	0.267	0.074	0.140	0.254	0.224	0.169	0.188	0.247
13	0.187	0.006	0.174	0.231	0.238	0.078	0.163	0.254	0.272	0.167	0.165	0.252
14	0.246	0.058	0.129	0.250	0.263	0.066	0.125	0.270	0.181	0.128	0.107	0.244
15	0.256	0.041	0.351	0.250	0.257	0.079	0.245	0.247	0.232	0.180	0.244	0.261
16	0.093	0.057	0.137	0.275	0.265	0.073	0.128	0.298	0.263	0.122	0.293	0.223
17	0.269	0.040	0.315	0.237	0.262	0.073	0.204	0.289	0.265	0.111	0.323	0.239
18	0.319	0.035	0.218	0.300	0.191	0.630	0.210	0.126	0.254	0.091	0.201	0.248

Table 10: Pairwise comparison matrix table for SGT responses

Exp.No	Ma.St	Mi.St	FT	DoF	Si+	Si-	Pi=Si+/(Si+)+(Si-)	RANK
1	0.00848	0.0047	0.07737	0.11734	0.05115	0.05098	0.50085	8
2	0.00723	0.0059	0.06158	0.12265	0.04013	0.03977	0.50225	7
3	0.00938	0.0037	0.03652	0.10527	0.01024	0.09566	0.09672	18
4	0.01121	0.0055	0.08642	0.15163	0.07711	0.02884	0.72780	2
5	0.00889	0.0047	0.05279	0.13135	0.03974	0.06581	0.37650	13
6	0.00851	0.0066	0.02989	0.11783	0.01998	0.09196	0.17851	17
7	0.01220	0.0067	0.05411	0.14583	0.05269	0.05651	0.48250	10
8	0.01026	0.0065	0.03856	0.12845	0.03100	0.07876	0.28245	15
9	0.00778	0.0066	0.07472	0.09948	0.04561	0.08018	0.36258	14
10	0.01005	0.0049	0.03615	0.12845	0.03016	0.08071	0.27205	16
11	0.00979	0.0036	0.09087	0.12845	0.06769	0.04812	0.58449	5
12	0.00811	0.0037	0.05098	0.13424	0.04115	0.06532	0.38648	11
13	0.00791	0.0005	0.05038	0.13424	0.04074	0.06600	0.38168	12
14	0.01042	0.0049	0.03736	0.14583	0.07966	0.07108	0.52845	6
15	0.01085	0.0035	0.10192	0.14583	0.08575	0.02996	0.74107	1
16	0.00393	0.0048	0.03989	0.16032	0.06255	0.06373	0.49534	9
17	0.01142	0.0034	0.09127	0.13811	0.07261	0.03908	0.65012	4
18	0.01351	0.0030	0.06339	0.17481	0.08248	0.03988	0.67411	3

Table 11: Ranking of alternatives for rolling direction

Exp.No	Ma.St	Mi.St	FT	DoF	Si+	Si-	Pi=Si+/(Si+)+(Si-)	RANK
1	0.00666	0.00647	0.07226	0.12869	0.07111	0.06543	0.52078	11
2	0.00731	0.00722	0.07951	0.13188	0.07818	0.06224	0.55676	7
3	0.00959	0.00553	0.06036	0.10635	0.04635	0.08496	0.35297	18
4	0.00734	0.00835	0.06965	0.14145	0.08004	0.05642	0.58656	5
5	0.00507	0.00769	0.06210	0.11911	0.05756	0.07335	0.43968	14
6	0.00802	0.00704	0.04875	0.09678	0.05624	0.09507	0.37169	16
7	0.01172	0.00760	0.08039	0.14783	0.09113	0.05300	0.63230	2
8	0.01055	0.00713	0.02786	0.13826	0.06490	0.07859	0.45230	13
9	0.00854	0.00685	0.07139	0.11273	0.05878	0.07714	0.43247	15
10	0.00874	0.00553	0.02902	0.14145	0.06814	0.07731	0.46848	12
11	0.01163	0.00572	0.08039	0.12869	0.07627	0.06578	0.53693	9
12	0.01131	0.00629	0.04063	0.14783	0.07554	0.06713	0.52947	10
13	0.01007	0.00666	0.04730	0.14783	0.07937	0.06302	0.55743	6
14	0.01114	0.00563	0.03628	0.15740	0.08444	0.06734	0.55633	8
15	0.01089	0.00675	0.07110	0.14358	0.08245	0.05655	0.59317	4
16	0.01123	0.00619	0.03715	0.17335	0.10040	0.06444	0.60910	3
17	0.01111	0.00619	0.05912	0.16804	0.09969	0.05255	0.65482	1
18	0.00808	0.05356	0.06085	0.07338	0.05838	0.10191	0.36423	17

Table 12: Ranking of Alternatives for Transverse Direction

Exp.No	Ma.St	Mi.St	FT	DoF	Si+	Si-	Pi=Si+/(Si+)+(Si-)	RANK
1	0.01086	0.01329	0.05877	0.10429	0.03929	0.05952	0.39762	15
2	0.00924	0.01126	0.04837	0.13420	0.05150	0.04914	0.51174	12
3	0.00751	0.00849	0.02269	0.11625	0.02681	0.08000	0.25103	17
4	0.00828	0.01200	0.08517	0.15215	0.08846	0.01003	0.89821	1
5	0.00889	0.01366	0.04041	0.12651	0.04131	0.05925	0.41082	14
6	0.00692	0.01403	0.03626	0.08975	0.01564	0.08485	0.15562	18
7	0.00642	0.01587	0.04928	0.09745	0.02929	0.07046	0.29361	16
8	0.01041	0.01642	0.06600	0.14703	0.07233	0.02842	0.71790	6
9	0.00977	0.01458	0.08146	0.12138	0.06711	0.03336	0.66795	7
10	0.01074	0.01698	0.05669	0.13420	0.05672	0.04133	0.57847	10
11	0.00957	0.01163	0.08580	0.13420	0.07731	0.02056	0.78993	3
12	0.00950	0.01439	0.05443	0.14361	0.06289	0.04036	0.60911	9
13	0.01152	0.01421	0.04801	0.14703	0.06295	0.04631	0.57614	11
14	0.00766	0.01089	0.03119	0.14190	0.05307	0.06362	0.45479	13
15	0.00985	0.01532	0.07070	0.15215	0.07911	0.02328	0.77265	4
16	0.01115	0.01033	0.08508	0.12993	0.07425	0.02518	0.74673	5
17	0.01124	0.00941	0.09367	0.13891	0.08635	0.01600	0.84367	2
18	0.01075	0.00775	0.05841	0.14438	0.06527	0.03752	0.63497	8

Table 13: Ranking of alternatives in Diagonal direction

	Exp	Ma.St	Mi.St	FT	DoF	Si+	Si-	Pi	RANK
Rolling High	15	0.01085	0.0035	0.10192	0.14583	0.08575	0.02996	0.74107	1
Rolling Low	3	0.00938	0.0037	0.03652	0.10527	0.01024	0.09566	0.09672	18
Transverse High	17	0.01111	0.00619	0.05912	0.16804	0.09969	0.05255	0.65482	1
Transverse Low	3	0.00959	0.00553	0.06036	0.10635	0.04635	0.08496	0.35297	18
Diagonal High	4	0.00828	0.01200	0.08517	0.15215	0.08846	0.01003	0.89821	1
Diagonal Low	6	0.00692	0.01403	0.03626	0.08975	0.01564	0.08485	0.15562	18

Table 14: Final top ranking of alternatives for all three directions

The Experimental results of all the three directions with their corresponding factors were optimized and ranked. The result which was ranked no 01 and 18 were chosen for SEM images because it denotes higher and lower formability.

D. Failure Topology

Fractography is the analysis of fractured features to determine the kind of fracture, such as ductile or brittle fractures, based on the nature of the fracture, formability, and relationships between the fractures. In addition, when n is low, it causes significant plastic deformation. The ductile fracture is characterised by prolate type voids with void expansion in thickness direction and more dimples. Below is an illustration of the fractured samples that were discovered

following straight groove tests under various strain situations. SEM pictures were used to observe the cracked surfaces, and optimization revealed that these images have

good formability in the three directions of rolling, transverse, and diagonal.

Fig. 3(a): Rolling 15 B-10 μm

Fig. 3(b): Rolling 15 B-100 μm

-Fig. 3(c): Transverse 17 B-10 μm

Fig. 3(d): Transverse 17B-100 μm

Fig. 3(e): Diagonal 4H-10 μm

Fig. 3(f): Diagonal 4H-100 μm

Fig. 3(a-f): SEM images of rolling, transverse and diagonal directions

The properties of the ductile fracture, including voids, particularly prolate voids that expand along the direction of thickness, intercrystalline slide, intercrystalline separation, intercrystalline fracture, as well as shear dimples, may be seen in the SEM pictures. Given that the material is cupro-nickel (90/10 Cu-Ni), the initial stage of the deformation results in inter crystalline slide, which progresses to inter crystalline separation, and the last stage results in inter crystalline fracture, revealing the ductility of the material. Under various magnifications, the SEM pictures of experiment number 15 with the ball tool, abbreviated as (15B), in the rolling direction of the straight groove test were presented. These images revealed the presence of prolate voids and intercrystalline separation that twined between the crystals.

The intercrystalline slide that precedes intercrystalline fracture as well as the characteristics of ductile fracture, such as shear dimples and prolate voids, are visible in the SEM images of the (17B) experiment taken in the transverse direction with greater formability in this direction after the straight groove test. SEM images of the experiment number 4 hemispherical ended tool (4H) in the diagonal direction exhibiting higher formability from the straight groove testing indicated prolate voids with inter crystalline slides, shear dimples. The voids increased in quantity when compared with the remaining two directions. This is due to the diagonal direction, when comparing the formability experiments, is totally at 45° to both rolling direction 0° and transverse direction 90°.

V. CONCLUSION

This analysis presents a new method; AHP-DENG'S Similarity based approach in optimizing straight groove test forming process parameters to obtain most suitable responses for formability analysis of cu-ni alloy during SPIF and conclusions of the above analysis:

- To obtain feasible forming process results, the input considerations and the best results Rolling, Transverse and Diagonal directions are as follows.
- Experiment No 15B, 17B and 4H- ranked No-1
- Ball Diameter tool 10,12 mm and 10 Hemispherical tool
- Speed-600,450 and 300 (RPM)
- Feed- 300 (mm/min) for all three directions.
- Lubricants –Grease.
- For lower feed, better values were obtained when grease was used as lubricants.
- The sum of strain values were found to high along the rolling direction, as the process takes place along the grain rolling direction.
- The sum of stain values were less when compared with rolling as the forming takes place perpendicular and angular to grain direction.
- The SEM image analysis shows the characteristics of ductile fracture with the presence of prolate voids.
- The ductile features were evidenced and failure topology shows the cu-ni material is ductile in nature as that of copper.

DECLARATION OF COMPETING INTEREST

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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REFERENCES

- [1.] Caron, R.N., 2001. Copper Alloys, Properties and Applications, Encyclopaedia of Materials: Science and Technology. Elsevier Inc. limited-1665–1668
- [2.] Shinhoo Kang, Peter K Domalavage, Nicholas Grant., 1986. Mechanical Properties of Rapidly Solidified Modified Cupro-Nickel Alloys, Materials Science and Engineering, Vol 78 Pages 33-44.
- [3.] Arun Prasad.M and C Sathiya Narayanan., 2022. Formability Analysis of Cupro-Nickel (90/10 Cu-Ni) during Single Point Incremental Forming Process.[Work Under review]
- [4.] Hepu Deng, 2007. A Similarity-Based Approach to Ranking Multicriteria Alternatives, ICIC 2007, LNAI 4682, Springer-Verlag Berlin Heidelberg, Pages 253–262.
- [5.] Suresh Kurra., Nasih HR., Srinivasaprakash Regalla and Amit Kumar Gupta 2014. Parametric study and multi-objective optimization in single-point incremental forming of extra deep drawing steel sheets. Proc IMechE Part B: Journal of Engineering Manufacture, Pages 1-13.
- [6.] Thomas L. Saaty 1990. How to make a decision: The Analytic Hierarchy Process, European Journal of Operational Research Vol 48, Pages 9-26.
- [7.] Phan Nguyen Huu., 2020 Multi-Objective Optimization in Titanium Powder Mixed Electrical Discharge Machining Process Parameters for Die Steels. Alexandria Engineering Journal Vol 59, Issue 6, Pages 4063-4079
- [8.] Pandivelan, C., Jeevanantham, A, K., 2014. Multi-Objective Optimization of Single Point Incremental Sheet Forming of AA5052 using Taguchi based Grey Relational Analysis Coupled with Principal Component Analysis .International Journal Of Precision Engineering And Manufacturing Vol. 15, No. 11, Pages 2309-2316.
- [9.] Honarpisheh, M., Mohammadi Jobedar, M., Alinaghian, I., 2018. Multi-Response Optimization on Single-Point Incremental Forming of Hyperbolic Shape Al-1050/Cu Bimetal Using Response Surface Methodology. The International Journal of Advanced Manufacturing Technology Vol 96, No (9-12), Pages 3069-3080.
- [10.] Hossein Safari, Ehsan Khanmohammadi, et al., 2013. A New Technique for Multi Criteria Decision Making Based on Modified Similarity

- Method.Middle-East Journal of Scientific Research
Vol 14 (5), Pages 712-719.
- [11.] Raju, C., Sathiya Narayanan, C., 2015. Application of a Hybrid Optimization Technique in a Multiple Sheet Single Point Incremental Forming Process Measurement Vol 78, Pages 296-308
- [12.] Pandivelan, C., Jeevanantham A K., Sathiyarayanan C., 2018. Optimization Study on Incremental Forming of Sheet Metal AA5052 for Variable Wall Angle using CNC Milling Machine ,Materials Today: Proceedings, Vol 5,Pages 12832–12836
- [13.] Anand Babu, K., Venkataramaiah, P., Dileep, P., 2017.AHP-DENG’S Similarity Based Optimization of WEDM Process Parameters of Al/SiCp Composite.American Journal of Materials Science and Technology.Vol. 6 No. 1, Pages 1-14.
- [14.] Binayak Sen., Mozammel Mia., Uttam Kumar Mandal et al., 2019. Multi-objective optimization for MQL-assisted end milling operation: an intelligent hybrid strategy combining GEP and NTOPSIS. Neural Computing and Applications Vol 31, Pages 8693–8717
- [15.] Duc- Nguyen Van., Bong- Pham Van., Phan- Nguyen Huu., 2019. Application of Deng’s similarity based – AHP approach in parametric optimization of EDM process for SDK11 die steel. Transactions of the Canadian Society for Mechanical Engineering Pages 1-27.